

Application of irradiance–temperature gradients to reveal coordinated shifts in phenolic compounds, non-structural carbohydrates, and biomass accumulation

Jan Pleva¹, Daniel Vrábl^{1,*}, Jakub Nezval¹, Petr Šmilauer², Radomír Pech¹, Adriana Volná¹, Éva Hideg¹, Nela Klusová¹ and Vladimír Špunda^{1,3}.

¹Department of Physics, Faculty of Science, University of Ostrava, Ostrava 710 00, Czech Republic and

²University of South Bohemia in České Budějovice, Faculty of science, Branišovská 1760, 370 05 České Budějovice.

³Global Change Research Institute, Czech Academy of Sciences, Brno 603 00, Czech Republic.

*For correspondence. E-mail daniel.vrabl@osu.cz.

Highlights:

- Gradient-based designs uncover interaction patterns missed by discrete experiments
- Continuous light–temperature gradients reveal nonlinear plant responses
- Irradiance primarily influences carbon pool size, temperature cues carbon allocation
- Phenolics track C/N status rather than carbon surplus alone

KEY WORDS

Gradient design, generalized additive models, light, temperature, biomass, phenolics, growth-defence trade-off.

ABSTRACT

Plant responses to environmental conditions are commonly assessed through experiments employing discrete treatment levels. However, such experimental approach may mask nonlinear responses and interaction regimes among the studied factors. To overcome these limitations, we examine *Arabidopsis thaliana* plants cultivated under continuous irradiance-temperature gradients and use generalized additive models to quantify light-temperature regulation of growth, carbon status and phenolics metabolism.

The patterns of estimated traits revealed by gradient-based experiments and generalized additive modelling are broadly consistent with conclusions derived from experiments at discrete irradiances and temperatures. However, this approach resolves, nonlinearities and interaction regimes that remain largely inaccessible to conventional factorial experiments. Across broad ranges of irradiance and, in particular, temperature, responses of most measured traits were non-linear, frequently exhibiting shifts between synergistic and antagonistic interactions.

Phenolic compounds increased with rising irradiance and decreasing temperature, except at temperatures above 40 °C, where their accumulation increased again. Irradiance is the dominant factor influencing the absolute size of the carbon pool, strongly enhancing biomass production, non-structural carbohydrate accumulation, and total phenolic content, while temperature is an important cue for carbon allocation between growth and defence. Microscopic analyses confirmed that whole-leaf phenolic patterns were accompanied by marked shifts in tissue-level flavonoid distribution, consistent with photoprotective and antioxidant functions.

In contrast to this clear environmental response, phenolic compound accumulation increased with non-structural carbohydrates only up to a certain point, after which further increases in phenolics were strongly associated with the C/N ratio, indicating regulation by integrated carbon–nutrient status rather than carbon surplus alone.

INTRODUCTION

Plants are continuously exposed to a range of environmental factors that influence photosynthetic activity, growth and tolerance through both synergistic and antagonistic effects. Light and temperature are among the most important environmental factors influencing plant function. Light serves as the primary source of energy, conserved in primary photoassimilates, particularly structural and non-structural carbohydrates (NSC; Wu et al., 2025). Temperature plays a more modulatory role, primarily affecting photosynthesis through its influence on enzymatic activity, respiration rates, and phloem transport (Moore et al., 2021; Vrábl et al., 2023). When temperature deviates from the optimal range, it substantially increases the production of reactive oxygen species, which in turn can damage the photosynthetic apparatus as a result of the peroxidation of membrane lipids, oxidation of proteins, and impairment of nucleic acids, while also affecting other cellular structures (Hasanuzzaman et al., 2013; Pospíšil, 2016). This effect is further enhanced under high irradiance. Under such suboptimal conditions, plants often increase the synthesis and accumulation of protective secondary metabolites with photoprotective and antioxidant functions, among which phenolic compounds (PheCs) play a prominent role (Pech et al., 2024).

A number of studies have examined how the combined effects of irradiance and temperature influence the production of assimilates and PheCs (Vrábl et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2022), and whether assimilate availability may constrain PheCs synthesis; however, their findings remain partly inconsistent. In many species, high irradiance is commonly associated with increased synthesis of flavonoids and anthocyanins that function as effective photoprotective and antioxidant agents (Agati and Tattini, 2010; Harborne and Williams, 2000). Similarly, exposure to low temperatures often enhances the accumulation of PheCs (Bilger et al., 2007; Shi et al., 2024), especially under strong light (Bhatia et al., 2018), where they help mitigate photodamage to the photosynthetic apparatus, particularly Photosystem II (Leonardelli et al., 2024; Pech et al., 2024). Conversely, elevated temperatures have been reported either to decrease phenolic compound concentrations, likely due to accelerated respiration and a consequent reduction in non-structural carbohydrate pools, or to induce specific groups of flavonoids (Grace and Logan, 2000; Vrábl et al., 2023). In contrast, several studies have observed increased phenolic accumulation following exposure to higher temperatures, for example in tomato and barley (Karamzadeh et al., 2025; Rivero et al., 2001). These discrepancies likely arise from synergistic and antagonistic interactions between temperature and irradiance that differentially influence photosynthetic activity and the production of protective metabolites. Consequently, variation in experimental design, exposure duration, species-specific responses, and the range or limiting levels of applied irradiance and temperature may lead to inconsistent outcomes across studies. This complexity underscores the need for approaches that capture plant responses across broad gradients of irradiance and temperature, as well as their interactions.

Conventional experimental approaches typically rely on single- or two-factor factorial designs to examine individual drivers or their interactions. However, such approaches are constrained by limited replication and a restricted number of tested factor levels, and they implicitly assume linear responses across a wide range of environmental drivers. In reality, plant responses to environmental conditions are often highly nonlinear, exhibiting thresholds, saturation effects, and strong interactions.

Typically, light and temperature, represent two of the most important ecophysiological drivers and the interplay between these factors can be either synergistic or antagonistic. In the range of suboptimal and optimal irradiance and temperatures, increasing irradiance and temperature have a predominantly synergistic effect on photosynthetic activity, whereas at temperatures above the optimum increasing irradiance tends to impose additional stress, resulting in an antagonistic interaction (Diao et al., 2024; Gamon and Pearcy, 1990; Pons, 2012). It is noteworthy that both responses are usually non-linear, with light generally following a non-rectangular hyperbolic pattern, whereas responses to temperature often exhibit a parabolic shape. Only when potential nonlinearity in physiological responses and interactions among these two environmental drivers is considered in experimental design, meaningful insights into the effects of individual factors within complex environments can be revealed, detecting important thresholds, interactions and non-linear relationships (Kreyling et al., 2014).

Gradient experimental designs, in which one or more environmental drivers vary continuously, allow responses to be assessed across many levels of the explanatory variable of interest. Compared with traditional experimental designs that typically test a few discrete treatment levels with replications, gradient approaches provide greater resolution for identifying nonlinear patterns, thresholds, and interactions. Simulation studies and controlled experiments have demonstrated that maximizing the number of levels along the gradient, even with little or no replication, increases predictive accuracy and the ability to recover true response shapes under realistic levels of random variation (Kreyling et al., 2018; Schweiger et al., 2016). When constrained by total sample size, allocating effort to a larger number of gradient levels rather than to replicates yields more informative results, particularly when the response surface is unknown or complex (Kreyling et al., 2018). Although replication remains important under conditions of high measurement noise and low systematic error (Schweiger et al., 2016), gradient designs offer a more efficient strategy for characterizing continuous responses, supporting model development, and improving mechanistic understanding of treatment effects.

As mentioned above, previous studies have typically examined plant physiological responses under a limited set of discrete irradiance and temperature levels, an approach that may obscure or misrepresent the interactive effects of these factors. To overcome this limitation, we designed a unique gradient experiment that enables the assessment of both the individual and combined impacts of irradiance and temperature on phenolic compound accumulation, NSC availability, and stress resistance across a continuous range of conditions. To capture potentially nonlinear and interactive responses across the full environmental gradient, we analysed the data using generalized additive models (GAMs). This approach further allows us to determine how these shifts in carbon allocation affect overall plant growth and to test whether the observed balance between investment in defence and biomass production aligns with growth–defence trade-off hypotheses.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant material, cultivation conditions and sample collection

Wild-type *Arabidopsis thaliana* (ecotype Columbia) plants were grown from seeds for six weeks under controlled conditions in a growth chamber (BioLine HB1014, Heraeus Vötsch, Germany). The plants were cultivated under a photosynthetic photon flux density (PPFD) of 100 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ of white polychromatic light, with a photoperiod of 8 h light/16 h dark. Day and night temperatures were maintained at 22 °C and 20 °C, respectively, and relative air humidity was kept at 60%. Plants were grown in plastic pots (390 mL) filled with a commercially available substrate Potgrond H (Klasman-Deilmann, Ltd. Germany). Throughout the entire cultivation period, plants were regularly watered to

ensure sufficient water availability, so that only the effects of irradiance and temperature could be evaluated.

After six weeks, the plants were acclimated for 14 days to experimental conditions consisting of a controlled gradient of irradiance ($40\text{--}1100\ \mu\text{mol m}^{-2}\ \text{s}^{-1}$) and temperature ($13\text{--}56\ ^\circ\text{C}$). The light gradient was established using an RGB LED panel (Smart Grow Light 300, Lightdrop, Czech Republic), and the temperature gradient was established using an infrared panel (HD-SWT700 Heat Decor, Heat Decor, Poland) oriented perpendicularly to LED panel, both positioned within the same growth chamber. The photoperiod remained unchanged, and the temperature gradient was maintained during both light and dark periods. No plant was in direct contact with the LED or infrared panels. Only plants labeled with white tags were selected for analysis, as shown in Fig. S1 (i.e., samples directly under the panel were not analyzed and served as reserve plants). Irradiance was measured at the soil level using a quantum sensor (Li-190R, Li-250A, Li-Cor, USA). Absolute temperature at each position within the matrix was measured prior to the start of the experiment by placing a black paper marker on each pot and recording its temperature using a thermal camera (E95, FLIR, USA). The black paper served as a standardized reference surface due to its high and uniform emissivity, providing a reliable estimate of the local ambient temperature. Actual leaf temperature was lower due to transpirational cooling and soil evaporation. Leaf temperature was assessed only indicatively during the experiment. Accurate leaf temperature measurements would have required targeting individual leaves with the thermal camera, which would have substantially disrupted the established thermal gradient. Therefore, only a few overview thermal images of the plants were acquired during acclimation to irradiance and temperature gradients to obtain a general indication of leaf temperature patterns. As this measurement was considered indicative rather than quantitative, the absolute temperature measured at each position prior to the start of the experiment was used in further analyses. Differences in leaf temperature among plants at different positions, arising from variation in transpirational cooling, were considered an inherent part of plant physiological responses to the thermal environment.

A total of 64 plants were used in the experiment. Due to the limited amount of biological material per individual plant, with each plant serving as one sampling point, every second plant ($n = 32$) was used for the analysis of NSC and PheCs. The remaining 32 plants were sampled for additional measurements that are not reported in this study. In addition, twelve plants were used for microscopic analysis of flavonoids. The plants for microscopy were selected to represent extreme and intermediate conditions within the temperature and irradiance gradient. Total biomass, including fresh and dry weight (D.W.), water content, and the carbon-to-nitrogen (C/N) ratio, was determined in all 64 plants. In addition, selected plants were assessed for the maximum quantum yield of photosystem II (Fv/Fm) using a FluorPen, and for epidermal UV-A shielding using a Dualex device.

Non-structural carbohydrates content

About 100 mg of fresh leaves were collected and frozen in liquid nitrogen after 14 days of acclimation to gradient conditions, 4 hours into the light period, i.e., in the middle of the photoperiod. The samples were subsequently freeze-dried (Labconco, Kansas City, MO, USA) and their dry weight was determined. For extraction, 0.5 mL of 80% aqueous methanol (v/v) (Honeywell, France) was used. The samples were heated for 15 minutes at $75\ ^\circ\text{C}$, then vacuum concentrated (CentriVap, Labconco, Kansas City, MO, USA), and the remaining pellet was resuspended in LC-MS grade water (VWR Chemicals, Rosny-sous-Bois, France). Non-structural carbohydrates were analysed using an ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography (UHPLC) system (Agilent Technologies 1260 Infinity II, Santa Clara, CA, USA) equipped with diode array (DAD), fluorescence (FLD), and refractive index (RID) detectors. Chromatographic separation was performed on a Pb^{2+} -based ion-exchange column (Polymer IEX Pb,

8.0 × 250 mm; Watrex, Prague, Czech Republic). The column compartment was maintained at 80 °C, and isocratic elution was carried out using LC-MS grade water (VWR Chemicals, Rosny-sous-Bois, France) as the mobile phase at a flow rate of 0.5 mL min⁻¹. The total run time was 45 min and the sample injection volume was 10 µl.

The RID served as the primary detector for NSC quantification (optical unit temperature 35 °C; zero offset 5%; attenuation 500,000 nRIU). The DAD and FLD detectors were used primarily for qualitative monitoring of potential co-eluting impurities or interferents, such as PheCs or photosynthetic pigments.

Compound identification was based on comparison of retention times with those of corresponding analytical standards analysed under identical chromatographic conditions. The quantification of individual compounds was based on established calibration curves of sucrose (Sucrose; ≥99.5% purity; Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA), glucose (D-(+)-Glucose; 99.5% purity; Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA), and fructose (D-(-)-Fructose; ≥99% purity; Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA). The NSC among samples was calculated as the sum of sucrose, glucose, and fructose content, normalized to sample D.W.

Soluble phenolic compounds content

The leaf material (50 mg fresh leaves of *Arabidopsis thaliana*) was homogenized with a small amount of sea sand (Penta chemicals, Praha, Czech Republic) in 3 ml of 40% methanol (CH₄O, ≥ 99.9%, Mr = 32.04 g mol⁻¹; Honeywell, Charlotte, NC, USA) using a mortar and pestle. The homogenate was ultrasonicated for 5 minutes (K-51E, Kraintek Czech, Hradec Králové, Czech Republic) and centrifuged (EBA 20, Hettich, Tuttlingen, Germany) at 6000 rpm for 3 minutes. The supernatant was adjusted to 3 ml with 40% methanol in a volumetric tube and filtered into a dark HPLC vial through syringe filters (Spartan filter, 13 mm, 0.2 µm, regenerated cellulose membrane; Whatman (Cytiva), Uppsala, Sweden). The prepared PheCs extracts were stored at -22 °C until analysis.

Semiquantitative analysis of PheCs extracts was performed using an Agilent 1200 HPLC system (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA) equipped with the UV-VIS diode array detector (DAD, G1315D). Phenolic compounds were separated on a Hypersil Gold chromatographic column (C18, 50 mm × 2.1 mm, 1.9 µm; Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA). The column was maintained at a constant temperature of 30 °C throughout the separation process.

The mobile phases consisted of two acetonitrile solutions: (A) 5% and (B) 80% acetonitrile (C₂H₃N, ≥ 99.9%, Mr = 41.05 g mol⁻¹; Honeywell, Charlotte, NC, USA) acidified with formic acid (CH₂O₂, Mr = 46.03 g mol⁻¹; Sigma-Aldrich (Merck), Darmstadt, Germany) in a ratio of 999:1 (v/v). The flow rate of the mobile phases was set at 0.3 ml min⁻¹. Details of the mobile phase gradient are provided in Tab. S1.

The injection volume was 10 µl. The relative quantity of PheCs was determined based on manual integration of peaks at 314nm, peak areas were adjusted to sample dry weight (peak area/D.W.), PheCs were assigned to the sinapate, anthocyanin, kaempferol, or quercetin derivatives sub-classes based on absorption spectra obtained from the DAD detector. The total content of soluble PheCs in each chromatogram was calculated as the sum of adjusted peak areas.

Estimation of carbon and nitrogen balance

The contents of carbon (C) and nitrogen (N) were determined in dry leaf samples using a CHN628 analyser (LECO Corporation, USA). Samples were combusted in an oxygen atmosphere at 950 °C, and

product oxides were quantified using infrared (C) and thermal conductivity (N) detectors to determine C and N concentrations. The obtained data were subsequently expressed as the C/N ratio.

UV-A shielding

The epidermal UV-A shielding index, representing the relative accumulation of flavonol-type compounds in the adaxial epidermal layer (Goulas et al., 2004), was assessed using a Dualex optical sensor (Force A, Orsay, France). Measurements were conducted at the end of the experimental period on eight-week-old plants, including a two-week acclimation phase under gradient conditions. Data were collected from the central region of fully expanded, age-matched leaves. All plants used for phenolic compound determination were included in the UV-A shielding measurements.

Maximum quantum yield of photosystem II (Fv/Fm)

In vivo measurements of Fv/Fm were performed using a FluorPen fluorometer (Photon Systems Instruments, Brno, Czech Republic). Measurements were conducted at the end of the experimental period on eight-week-old plants, including a two-week acclimation phase under gradient conditions. Data were collected from the central region of fully expanded leaves of comparable developmental stage. Measurements were performed under dark conditions approximately 30 minutes before the onset of the light phase.

Microscopy methods

For the microscopic detection of flavonoids, a Naturstoff reagent (0.25% w/v) was used. A total of 0.125 g of 2-aminoethyl diphenylborinate (DPBA; Sigma-Aldrich, USA) was dissolved in 5 mL of water together with 2.5 μ L of Triton X (Sigma-Aldrich, USA). After the DPBA was fully dissolved, the solution was diluted to a final volume of 50 mL.

From each of the 12 plants, one leaf was collected, and three transverse sections were prepared. The sections were immediately transferred into the Naturstoff reagent on a microscope slide. All three sections were observed simultaneously using a fluorescence microscope Olympus BX53F (Olympus Corporation, Japan), and images were captured from each section with a Nikon D780 camera (Nikon Corporation, Japan). One representative section is presented in Fig. 5 (see Results).

Data visualisation and statistical analysis

All analyses were conducted in R 4.5.0 (R Core Team 2025) using the *vegan* and *mgcv* packages. Multivariate trait relationships were analysed by redundancy analysis (RDA) (Legendre and Legendre, 2012) with temperature and PPFD as explanatory variables. Traits were centred and standardised, and significance was assessed by permutation tests with 99,999 permutations. Results are reported as adjusted R^2 (adj. R^2) together with overall, axis-wise and by-term effects. Trait-wise responses were analysed using generalised additive models (Hastie and Tibshirani, 1986). These models included univariate smooth terms and their tensor-product interaction for PPFD by Temperature. Additional GAMs were used to explore trait to trait relationships, including additive models, interaction models based on tensor-product smooths, and bivariate smooths for visualisation of joint response surfaces. Model adequacy was evaluated using standard diagnostic procedures, including residual patterns, basis-dimension checks and concurvity. Results were summarised by sample size (n), Effective Degrees of Freedom (EDF), adj. R^2 and smooth-term test statistics. Predicted reaction surfaces were restricted to the convex hull of the observed data to avoid unsupported extrapolation. Where indicated, only mild extrapolation of up to fifteen percent beyond the hull was allowed. Interaction signs were classified from the mixed second partial derivative of the fitted surfaces, which was numerically approximated

from model predictions. Near-zero values were interpreted as boundary regions, positive values as synergistic interactions and negative values as antagonistic interactions. To reduce the influence of extreme values, improve linearity and stabilise variance, response variables with a natural zero point, including dry weight, fresh weight (F.W.), NSC, PheCs and UV-A shielding, were ln-transformed. Among predictors, only PPFD was ln-transformed due to its wide range and natural zero, whereas temperature was analysed on the original scale.

RESULTS

Redundancy analysis

Redundancy analysis revealed a clear structuring of plant functional traits along the combined gradients of PPFD and temperature (Fig. 1). The RDA model was highly significant (permutation test, 99,999 permutations; $p < 0.001$) and explained a substantial proportion of the variability in the response matrix (adj. $R^2 = 0.508$). Both explanatory variables contributed significantly to the model, with highly significant effects of PPFD ($p < 0.001$) and temperature ($p < 0.001$). The first canonical axis (RDA1), explaining 35.9% of the total variance, was primarily associated with PPFD, whereas the second axis (RDA2; 17.6%) reflected variation related mainly to temperature.

Growth-related traits showed strong projections onto the ordination axes and responded consistently to both environmental gradients. Dry weight was aligned with the PPFD-related axis, and also showed a clear association with the temperature-related axis indicating that D.W. increased with increasing irradiance as well as with increasing temperature. Fresh weight exhibited a similar increase with PPFD but showed a relatively stronger association with the temperature gradient compared with D.W., indicating a pronounced increase in fresh biomass with rising temperature. The C/N ratio displayed one of the longer vectors in the biplot, suggesting a strong contribution to the ordination structure. It increased with increasing PPFD, while showing an opposing response to the temperature, indicating higher C/N ratios under high irradiance and lower temperatures.

In contrast, metabolic and photoprotective traits showed more selective response patterns. Nonstructural carbohydrates were characterized by a short vector oriented mainly along the PPFD-related axis, indicating that NSC content increased with increasing irradiance, while showing just a little change along the temperature gradient. Total amounts of leaf PheCs showed opposing responses to the two environmental drivers, with their projection along the PPFD-related axis indicating increasing concentrations with increasing irradiance, whereas their strong alignment with the temperature-related axis in the opposite direction indicated decreasing concentrations with increasing temperature. The epidermal UV-A shielding responded even more sensitively to irradiance than the total PheCs content, however its correlation with temperature was weaker.

Generalized additive models of trait responses to PPFD and temperature

The GAM analyses revealed distinct and often interactive effects of PPFD and temperature on physiological and biochemical traits (Figs. 2–3). For consistency, GAMs were fitted for all response variables irrespective of the statistical significance of the PPFD \times temperature interaction (Table 1). Where the interaction term was not significant, interpretation focused on the additive main effects, which are appropriately illustrated by partial effect plots (Fig. 2 b, c; Fig. 4). When a statistically significant PPFD \times temperature interaction was detected, interpretation was based on the full GAM response surfaces, because partial effect plots depict only marginal additive effects and do not represent the interaction structure. Accordingly, inference in such cases was drawn primarily from the GAM response surfaces (Fig. 3), while partial effect plots (Fig. 4) were used only for inspection of the marginal trends.

Maximum PSII quantum efficiency, expressed as F_v/F_m (Fig. 2), was primarily driven by temperature, showing pronounced decline at higher temperatures ($p < 0.001$), whereas PPFD alone had no significant effect ($p \geq 0.05$). A significant PPFD \times temperature interaction was detected ($p < 0.05$), although the effect was relatively weak compared to the dominant role of temperature. Partial effect plots confirmed this pattern, showing that at lower temperatures, higher PPFD slightly elevated F_v/F_m values. At elevated temperatures ($>30^\circ\text{C}$), however, the negative impact of heat stress outweighed any influence of PPFD, resulting in a consistent decline.

Biomass production responded strongly to both predictors. Dry weight (Fig. 3a) exhibited highly significant main effects of PPFD and temperature ($p < 0.001$ for both), with a high adj. R^2 (0.83; Tab. 1). The greatest biomass accumulation was observed with increasing PPFD, and this positive effect was supported by temperature up to approximately 40°C . Above this threshold, elevated temperatures exerted a negative influence that counteracted the stimulatory role of PPFD. Importantly, because the PPFD \times temperature interaction was highly significant ($p < 0.001$), the response of D.W. cannot be fully captured by the partial effects of the individual predictors shown in (Fig. 4a). The full GAM surface (Fig. 3a) therefore provides more accurate representation of how the combined effects of light and temperature determined biomass accumulation.

By contrast, the C/N ratio, which reflects plant carbon–nitrogen allocation, was highest under conditions of high PPFD combined with lower temperatures (Fig. 3b). The PPFD \times temperature interaction was not significant ($p \geq 0.05$), whereas the main effects of PPFD ($p < 0.001$) and temperature ($p < 0.001$) were both highly significant, allowing a more straightforward interpretation of the predictors individual effects. Partial effect plots (Fig. 4b) show a linear increase of C/N with rising PPFD, while temperature exerted a gradual negative effect, together resulting in the highest C/N ratios under high PPFD and lower temperatures.

Patterns in carbon allocation between primary and secondary metabolism were further characterized by the responses of NSC and PheCs, which were examined in relation to a potential growth–defence balance. Both traits showed significant dependencies on PPFD, but differed in their responses to temperature and its interaction with PPFD.

For NSC, the PPFD \times temperature interaction was highly significant ($p < 0.001$), as was the main effect of PPFD ($p < 0.01$), whereas the main effect of temperature was not statistically significant ($p \geq 0.05$). Because of the significant interaction, NSC responses were interpreted based on the full GAM response surface (Fig. 3c), which showed predominantly increasing concentrations with increasing PPFD across most of the gradient, while elevated NSC levels also occurred under low PPFD combined with very high temperatures.

In contrast, PheCs were significantly influenced by both PPFD ($p < 0.001$) and temperature ($p < 0.001$) as main effects, whereas their interaction was not significant ($p \geq 0.05$), allowing interpretation based on partial effect plots (Fig. 4d). PheCs concentrations decreased with rising temperature up to approximately 40°C and then showed a slight increase at higher temperatures. With increasing PPFD, PheCs concentrations increased but showed early indications of saturation, in contrast to the near-linear increase observed for NSC (Fig. 4c), indicating that further increases in irradiance may result in comparatively smaller changes in PheCs than in NSC.

Epidermal UV-A shielding (Fig. 3e) was significantly influenced by both PPFD ($p < 0.001$) and temperature ($p < 0.001$), and their interaction was also significant ($p < 0.05$), indicating that the effects of irradiance and temperature on UV-A shielding were not strictly additive. The response surface revealed a strong increase in UV-A shielding with increasing PPFD across most of the temperature

gradient, whereas temperature modulated this response in an interactive manner. The highest UV-A shielding values occurred under high irradiance, particularly at lower and intermediate temperatures, while low PPFD was consistently associated with low shielding across the temperature range. Because of the significant interaction, UV-A shielding responses are best interpreted from the full GAM response surface (Fig. 3e), while partial effect plots (Fig. 4e) illustrate a near-linear increase with PPFD and a non-linear response to temperature, characterized by an initial decline followed by a tendency to increase at very high temperatures, a pattern that parallels the temperature response observed for PheCs.

When PheCs content was expressed relative to biomass (PheCs/D.W.; Fig. 3f), the response surface revealed distinct interaction patterns between PPFD and temperature. Both PPFD ($p < 0.05$) and temperature ($p < 0.001$) had significant main effects, and their interaction was also significant ($p < 0.01$). The highest PheCs/D.W. values, indicating a strong investment in defense relative to growth, occurred at low temperatures, particularly under low PPFD. In contrast, the lowest ratios were observed at higher PPFD combined with intermediate temperatures, reflecting conditions that favor biomass production over defensive investment. The effects of PPFD and temperature were not uniform across the gradient. At low and high temperatures, the two drivers acted synergistically, whereas at intermediate temperatures their effects were antagonistic.

Tissue-level flavonoid distribution assessed by fluorescence microscopy

To assess whether and how the observed environmentally driven shifts in PheCs were reflected at the leaf tissue level, we used fluorescence microscopy. Flavonoids localization, identified as Naturstoff fluorescence, was mainly PPFD dependent, and low temperature had only a minor positive effect (Fig. 5). Low temperature-induced flavonoid accumulation was particularly evident under low irradiances ($<50 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$; Fig. 5: C11, C12). Under high temperature and low irradiance conditions (Fig. 5: R1C12), flavonoid concentrations were barely detectable and tended to increase with decreasing temperature, mainly in the epidermis and adjacent cell layers (both adaxial and abaxial). At such low irradiance, an unequal distribution of flavonoids was clearly visible, with higher concentrations in guard cells. Moreover, the difference in spectral properties of flavonoid-Naturstoff complex fluorescence emission (compare, e.g., Fig. 5: R7C12 \times R7C2 i.e. samples acclimated to rather low temperature but different irradiance) also suggest qualitative changes in PheCs profiles. Intensive flavonoid accumulation was observed under high irradiance ($>500 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$; Fig. 5: C1, C2), whereas the positive effect of low temperature was barely detectable. Under such conditions, flavonoids accumulated mainly in the adaxial and abaxial epidermis. On the abaxial side, there was a distinct boundary between the epidermis and the parenchyma, whereas on the adaxial side, flavonoids were significantly accumulated also deeper in the adjacent parenchyma cell layer.

Bivariate GAMs linking carbon allocation, nutritional status, and growth

To further examine how carbon allocation between primary and secondary metabolism relates to plant growth and nutritional status, we applied generalized additive models using combinations of NSC, PheCs, and the C/N ratio as predictors. We first fitted additive models with separate smooth functions for each predictor ($s(x) + s(y)$) and subsequently included tensor-product interaction terms ($ti(x, y)$) to explicitly test for non-additive effects. In neither relationship did the interaction term significantly improve model fit, indicating no strong evidence for non-additive effects between the predictors (Table 2; Tab. S2). In contrast, bivariate smooth models (Fig. 6, Tab. 2) revealed highly significant joint

nonlinear response surfaces for both predictor combinations, confirming that plant growth and secondary metabolism are structured by coupled, nonlinear relationships between carbon status and nutritional traits. Because the primary aim of this analysis was to visualise these joint effects rather than to interpret partial effects separately, reaction surfaces are presented using bivariate smooth models $s(x, y)$; Fig. 6).

The bivariate model describing PheCs as a function of NSC and the C/N ratio (Fig. 6a) explained a smaller but still meaningful proportion of variability (adj. $R^2 = 0.25$). While both NSC and C/N had highly significant main effects on PheCs ($p < 0.001$), their interaction was not statistically significant ($p = 0.1387$), indicating independent contributions of carbohydrate availability and nutritional status to phenolic accumulation. Across the response surface, PheCs concentrations increased predominantly with increasing C/N ratio.

In contrast, the bivariate model relating D.W. to the joint variation in PheCs and the C/N ratio (Fig. 6b) showed moderate explanatory power (adj. $R^2 = 0.45$). The model revealed a significant interaction between the two predictors ($p = 0.0379$), and the bivariate smooth term was also highly significant ($p < 0.001$). Together, these results indicate that the relationship between PheCs investment and biomass depended on plant nutritional status. Dry weight reached its highest values at relatively low phenolic concentrations combined with high C/N ratios, whereas the lowest biomass was observed at high phenolic concentrations and intermediate C/N ratios.

DISCUSSION:

Nonlinearities, interactions and thresholds identified using a continuous environmental gradient model

We found that irradiance and temperature jointly regulate growth, carbon status, and phenolic metabolism in *Arabidopsis thaliana* plants. The nonlinear responses of analyzed variables and frequent interactions detected across the irradiance and temperature gradient underline the appropriateness of employing a continuous experimental design in this study. As noted by Kreyling et al. (2014), this approach, in addition to its efficiency, also offers conceptual advantages, as it enables a mechanistic interpretation of how multiple environmental factors jointly shape physiological responses and can reveal transition zones or instabilities that indicate physiological thresholds or tipping points. In our experiment, these features were particularly evident, as the responses of the measured variables and their combined effects alternated between synergy and antagonism across the gradient. This behavior was clearly visible in the GAM response surfaces (Figs. 2, 3 and 6), where the sign of the interaction term ($\partial^2 z / \partial x \partial y$) was changing across irradiance and temperature range. Such interaction patterns, as highlighted by previous studies (Kreyling et al., 2018; Schweiger et al., 2016), would have been difficult to capture using a traditional factorial experimental design with a limited number of discrete treatments. Both simulations and empirical evidence indicate that allocating sampling effort across multiple gradient levels allows testing a greater number of interactions and nonlinear responses than traditional replicated factorial designs (De Boeck et al., 2015; Kreyling et al., 2018). The value of replication, however, depends on the dominant source of variability. When random noise is high, replication becomes critical for reliable inference. In contrast, when systematic sources of variability dominate, experimental designs that incorporate realistic variation or gradient-based treatments may be more informative than replicated fixed-level designs (Schweiger et al., 2016; Thompson et al., 2013). Given that our controlled laboratory setup minimized random variability, maximizing the number of gradient levels was the most effective approach for detecting thresholds, interaction reversals and nonlinear curvature in the responses.

Multivariate ordination reveals contrasting growth; primary, and secondary metabolite responses to combined environmental drivers

A coherent interpretation of these nonlinear and interaction-driven patterns requires not only analysing individual response shapes but also integrating them across all measured variables. Redundancy analysis (Fig. 1) showed that growth-related traits, epidermal UV-A shielding, and the C/N ratio were most strongly aligned with the environmental gradients, which highlights the coordinated influence of PPFD and temperature on plant performance. The orientation of these vectors across RDA1 and RDA2 indicates that growth responses arise from the joint action of irradiance and temperature, a pattern that has been widely documented in studies examining light–temperature interactions in plant physiology. Valladares and Niinemets (2008) emphasized that light availability modulates a broad suite of functional traits, while temperature simultaneously constrains metabolic rates and carbon gain, resulting in tightly coupled growth responses under combined environmental gradients. While Poorter et al. (2019) quantified generalized dose–response relationships of plant traits to irradiance alone, our results extend this framework by demonstrating how these light-driven responses are reshaped under concurrent temperature gradient, revealing interaction structures that remain hidden in single-factor syntheses. Our RDA therefore captures a well-established pattern in which both light and thermal environments jointly determine the overall growth syndrome rather than acting independently. In contrast, the short vectors of metabolites, particularly primary NSC, show that their variability was explained much weaker than growth or C/N. The near perpendicular orientation of NSC and PheCs vectors does not imply biological independence of the two pathways but rather reflects their contrasting allocation mechanisms in response to environmental gradients. NSC represent a rapidly changing pool of glucose, fructose, and sucrose that is kept relatively stable even under environmental fluctuations because it serves as a primary source of energy and carbon for basal metabolism (Hartmann and Trumbore, 2016; Sala et al., 2012). Phenolic secondary metabolites, by contrast, reflect carbon investment into defensive and photoprotective processes whose synthesis is much more sensitive to light and temperature extremes. Strong induction of the phenylpropanoid pathway under low temperatures or high irradiance is well documented (Agati and Tattini, 2010; Grace and Logan, 2000; Zoratti et al., 2014). The fact that PheCs in our biplot point toward high PPFD and low temperature therefore corresponds to the concept that secondary metabolism draws only a limited fraction of carbon flow and is activated when the plant needs to increase antioxidant capacity or UV shielding, while NSC are maintained within a relatively stable range to secure the carbon supply for growth and respiration. This contrasting response pattern between rapid primary metabolism and inducible secondary metabolism is consistent with current understanding of trade-offs between growth and defense and with carbon allocation theory under stress conditions (Herms and Mattson, 1992; Stamp, 2003), as evidenced in our results.

Light and Low Temperature Co-action Cause Activation of Phenolic Compound Metabolism via Photoreceptor Signaling

Photoreceptor-mediated signaling, operating mainly via transcriptional control, is a key regulatory framework governing the observed patterns of total PheCs content (Figs. 3d, 4d) across irradiance and temperature gradients. The positive, near linear response of PheCs to increasing irradiance under UV excluded conditions is consistent with enhanced activity of light signaling pathways known to promote phenylpropanoid metabolism. This regulation involves the transcription factor HY5, an important regulator of photomorphogenesis and a key positive regulator of structural genes of the flavonoid and

anthocyanin biosynthetic pathways (Xiao et al., 2022). HY5 promotes PheC accumulation by binding to promoters of essential structural genes (e.g. CHS, CHI, F3'H, DFR, ANS) and by positively regulating additional transcription factors such as MYB12 and MYB75 (Shin et al., 2013). Activation of cryptochromes and phytochromes by photosynthetically active radiation inhibits COP1, a major repressor of HY5, thereby favouring PheC accumulation. Blue light perception by cryptochromes appears particularly important for efficient PheC production and for increasing the relative abundance of phenolics with high antioxidant capacity, enhancing tolerance to photo oxidative stress during acclimation to high irradiance (Brelsford et al., 2019; Pech et al., 2022; Taulavuori et al., 2016) , although sensitivity to blue light is species specific (Larsen et al., 2022; Taulavuori et al., 2016).

In our study, PheC content decreased with increasing temperature up to approximately 40 °C, whereas temperatures above this threshold promoted a slight increase in accumulation (Fig. 4d). The synergistic effects of high irradiance and low temperature may be related to low temperature induced nuclear exclusion of COP1, which alleviates repression of HY5 (Catalá et al., 2011), as well as to stabilisation of the active form of cryptochromes (CRY2), which interact with COP1 in a manner that limits HY5 degradation (Li et al., 2021) . In contrast, elevated temperatures may negatively affect PheC production through thermal reversion of active phytochromes (particularly phyB) to their inactive form, leading to reduced HY5 abundance and stabilisation of phytochrome interacting factors (PIFs), which act as repressors of phenolic biosynthesis, especially of anthocyanins.

Despite the expected suppression of HY5 dependent signaling and increased PIF activity at high temperatures, PheC levels exhibited a slight increase above 40 °C (Fig. 3d). This response suggests that under extreme thermal conditions additional regulatory mechanisms, such as ROS mediated signaling, may become increasingly important in the regulation of phenolic metabolism.

A possible link between the regulation of primary and secondary metabolites

In the context of a potential growth–defence balance strategy, patterns of carbon allocation between primary and secondary metabolism were inferred from the response patterns observed for NSC and PheCs (Figs. 3 c, d and 4 c, d). Non-structural carbohydrates serve as a central carbon pool and provide substrates for the biosynthesis of secondary metabolites, including PheCs, whose synthesis is dynamically modulated in response to biotic and abiotic stressors. The observed increase in NSC with increasing irradiance is consistent with enhanced carbon assimilation and suggests that carbon availability is a primary driver of NSC storage under favourable light conditions. This interpretation is further supported by the tendency for higher NSC accumulation under conditions promoting photosynthetic activity, whereas elevated NSC concentrations under low PPFD and temperature extremes likely reflect sink limitation rather than enhanced carbon assimilation, resulting in reduced utilization of assimilates for growth (Fig 3c, 3a) . In addition to serving as metabolic substrates, specific NSC forms, including sucrose and trehalose-6-phosphate, may also act as signaling molecules that modulate PheCs biosynthesis through signaling pathways involving HXK, SnRK1, and TOR, thereby linking assimilate status with secondary metabolism as review by Eom et al. (2024). Sucrose-dependent regulation of PheCs biosynthesis was observed at the gene-expression level. For example, chalcone synthase was found to be induced by sucrose signalling (Solfanelli et al., 2006). Additionally, chalcone synthase is regulated by the transcription factor MYB75, whose expression is directly induced by sucrose concentration (Teng et al., 2005).

Sucrose-dependent regulation of secondary metabolism does not operate in isolation but is integrated into broader nutrient sensing networks that coordinate growth and defense allocation. The results in Fig. 3b (C/N) and Fig. 3c (NSC) reflect the plant's energy and carbon status. Under high light and

moderate temperatures, the plant accumulates more carbon (higher C/N) and NSCs, indicating an abundance of energy and photosynthetic products. Nutrient sufficiency activates the serine/threonine protein kinase TOR, the main anabolic regulator that supports biomass synthesis and growth. Recent work has shown that TOR activity is modulated by carbon fixation through the intracellular abundance of specific amino acids, with the strongest effects observed for glutamine, alanine, glycine, and cysteine (Cao et al., 2019; Liu et al., 2021; Mallén-Ponce et al., 2022). Suppression of TOR leads to a rapid increase in nitrogen uptake and an upregulation of amino acid synthesis, which may serve as a feedback mechanism to restore TOR activity and maintain metabolic homeostasis. Thus, TOR has been proposed to integrate both carbon and nitrogen signals and to regulate their interconnection (Artins et al., 2024).

Surprisingly, carbon was also stored intensively in NSCs under low PPFD combined with extremely high temperatures (Fig. 3c), which may result from strongly reduced growth. Under such extreme conditions (low PPFD and temperatures above 40 °C), elevated NSC levels may also result from autophagy (Artins et al., 2024). Autophagy is a key pathway activated during energy-limiting conditions by the SnRK1 protein kinase, which plays a crucial role in plant survival under low-energy states triggered by various stresses (Margalha et al., 2016). SnRK1 activation suppresses growth-related processes and promotes a shift toward catabolism. Concurrently, low energy status leads to downregulation of TOR signaling, resulting in starch accumulation and a dramatic increase in amino acid levels (Artins et al., 2024). Together, these processes may explain the high NSC content (Fig. 3c) and low C/N ratio (Fig. 3b) observed under low PPFD and elevated temperature.

Against this mechanistic background, differences in carbon availability and metabolic status provide the physiological context in which environmental drivers shape carbon allocation patterns. Our results indicate that temperature is the primary environmental factor associated with variation in the relative allocation of assimilated carbon between structural biomass and defence compounds, as reflected by changes in the phenolic-to-biomass ratio (Rivero et al., 2001). In contrast, irradiance strongly affects the absolute size of the carbon pool through its control of carbon assimilation, with the potential to markedly increase both biomass production and the total amount of defensive compounds (Jaakola and Hohtola, 2010; Vrábl et al., 2023). Consequently, light availability may primarily control overall defence capacity by increasing total and photoprotective phenolic pools. In contrast, temperature regulates how available energy or carbon is allocated between growth and defence. This distinction is consistent with and broader evidence that warming and carbon supply can have contrasting (and sometimes interactive) effects on carbon-based defences and related plant traits, depending on whether defensive investment is evaluated as absolute amount of protective compound or expressed relative to biomass or carbon gain (Sobuj et al., 2018).

Environmental gradients drive tissue-specific flavonoid distribution and functional specialization

To complement whole-leaf biochemical measurements, fluorescence microscopy was employed to evaluate whether the observed environmental responses were reflected in tissue-specific patterns of flavonoid accumulation in *Arabidopsis thaliana* leaves (Fig. 5). Overall, tissue-level observations were consistent with whole-leaf trends in total soluble PheC content. Under conditions presumed to impose low oxidative pressure (low irradiance, absence of temperature extremes) and limited inductive photoreceptor-driven signaling, flavonoids accumulated primarily in the adaxial (more pronounced) and abaxial epidermis or in closely neighbouring cell layers. This pattern can be considered constitutive flavonoid production, and their near-surface localisation may be related to their primary UV-screening function, as well as to the fact that irradiance is highest at the adaxial side and sufficient to activate

PheCs production, whereas deeper within the leaf the required light thresholds are not reached (Pech et al., 2022). With increasing irradiance acting synergistically with more extreme temperatures, flavonoid accumulation progressively expanded from the palisade parenchyma into deeper regions of the spongy parenchyma, where they likely act as antioxidants rather than UV attenuators (Nichelmann and Pescheck, 2021). Accordingly, the relative content of quercetin derivatives increased, as indicated by strong yellow fluorescence of the DPBA–quercetin complex (Lewis et al., 2011; Nguyen et al., 2017). Compounds derived from quercetin remain efficient antioxidants even after common modifications such as 3-O-glycosylation (Csepregi and Hideg, 2018) and thus may substantially contribute to total antioxidant defence in photosynthetically active tissues subjected to excessive PAR and non-optimal temperature. However, this accumulation of flavonoids also resulted in a pronounced increase in epidermal UV-A shielding, suggesting a potentially significant cross-acclimation to UV-induced stress. In contrast, at low irradiance and low temperatures, overall flavonoid content was low, and the kaempferol-to-quercetin ratio was higher, as inferred from the prevailing green fluorescence of the DPBA–kaempferol complex as opposed to the yellow fluorescence of the DPBA–quercetin complex (Azar et al., 1987). This suggests that under low temperatures the early steps of the flavonoid pathway remain partially active, whereas subsequent structural modifications, such as B-ring dihydroxylation, require light activation. This interpretation is consistent with the fact that *Arabidopsis* preferentially accumulates kaempferol derivatives under non-stressed conditions (Jones et al., 2003; Schulz et al., 2015).

Intriguingly, enhanced flavonoid accumulation was also observed in guard cells, supporting a potential role in modulating ROS signaling and stomatal function (Watkins et al., 2017). This spatial pattern suggests a protective function in maintaining redox homeostasis in tissues exposed to rapid fluctuations of water status and directly exposed to environmental stressors.

Gradient-based evidence for growth–defence trade-offs mediated by carbon status

In line with above described carbon allocation patterns, the generalized additive models of the interactive effects, predicting accumulation of PheCs (Fig. 6a) at the base of C/N ratio, enabled us to test and visualize the overall relationships between these variables. Based on the results, the highest accumulation of PheCs is predicted to occur under increasing C/N ratios, which arise as carbon availability increases. However, at high NSC concentrations we observe a saturation effect, where further increases in PheC levels occur only as a consequence of rising C/N ratios rather than additional NSC accumulation itself. Similar trends have been demonstrated in classical replication experiments in which either nitrogen availability (Bot et al., 2009; Royer et al., 2013) or atmospheric CO₂ concentration (Penuelas et al., 1997) was manipulated. In these studies, higher C/N ratios were consistently associated with increased PheC accumulation.

To test the competitive relationship between PheCs synthesis and biomass production a generalized additive model was constructed, allowing the prediction of biomass production based on the leaf C/N ratio and PheC content. The results clearly show that the highest biomass accumulation is associated with high C/N ratio and low PheCs, whereas low biomass production coupled with elevated PheCs accumulation is linked to an average C/N ratio (Fig. 6a, 6b). An overall examination of the response surface reveals that decreases in D.W. are consistently associated with pronounced increases in PheC content or reductions in the C/N ratio (in our case driven primarily by declines in C). Conversely, increases in D.W. are consistently linked to lower PheC levels or elevated C/N ratios. Because the plants in this experiment were supplied with nitrogen in non-limiting amounts, the observed variation in biomass C/N ratios largely reflected variation in carbon content. These findings align with the ecological concept that elevated concentrations of carbon-rich secondary metabolites, which occur in greater amounts under low nitrogen availability or, more generally, in plants with high C/N ratios, arise

from mass-action–driven shifts in metabolism. When nitrogen becomes limiting and carbon can no longer be effectively invested in growth and the surplus carbon is redirected into the synthesis of carbon-rich protective compounds (Endara and Coley, 2011; Ferrenberg et al., 2023; Glynn et al., 2007; Penuelas et al., 1997).

Although our results are broadly consistent with the predictions of the Growth–Defense Trade-off framework, it is important to acknowledge that several studies, including Koricheva (2002), have highlighted conceptual weaknesses and the limited long-term sustainability of this framework. One reason for these discrepancies may be that conventional repetitive experiments often operate within a narrow range of predictor variables (e.g., restricted environmental conditions), which constrains their ability to capture the full scope of physiological responses. Gradient-based experimental designs therefore offer a more suitable approach, as they enable the detection of interactions among key factors across wide ecological ranges and multiple levels of intensity. Such designs can reveal deviations from the outcomes predicted by individual frameworks and help identify conditions under which these conceptual models may fail.

CONCLUSION

To clarify the complementary roles of the analytical approaches used, RDA summarizes the dominant directions of multivariate trait covariation along environmental gradients, indicating which traits covary and in which direction. However, RDA does not resolve nonlinear response shapes, thresholds, or reversals in interaction effects. In contrast, GAMs describe how individual traits change across continuous gradients, capturing nonlinear responses, shifts between synergistic and antagonistic effects, and extreme responses across the environmental space.

Our results demonstrate that irradiance and temperature regulate plant performance through fundamentally different but interacting mechanisms. Irradiance primarily controlled the absolute carbon pool, strongly enhancing biomass production, non-structural carbohydrate accumulation, and total phenolic content. In contrast, temperature emerged as the main driver of carbon allocation, determining how assimilated carbon was partitioned between growth and defence. This distinction became evident when defence investment was expressed relative to biomass, revealing temperature-dependent shifts in growth–defence balance that were not apparent from absolute trait values alone. Response surfaces revealed pronounced nonlinearity and systematic reversals between synergistic and antagonistic interactions across the gradients, indicating distinct physiological regimes rather than a single, uniform response pattern. Phenolic accumulation did not simply scale with carbon availability but reflected coordinated regulation by environmental stress and plant nutritional status.

Overall, our findings show that gradient-based experiments combined with flexible nonlinear modelling provide a powerful framework for identifying thresholds, interaction reversals, and trade-off structures in plant physiology. This approach offers mechanistic insight into how interacting environmental drivers shape carbon allocation and defence strategies, with clear relevance for understanding plant responses under increasingly variable climatic conditions.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

J.P., D.V., and J.N. contributed to conceptualization, methodology, experimental design, and writing – original draft preparation. J.P. contributed to investigation, formal analysis, data curation, and visualization. D.V. contributed to investigation, sample collection, biochemical analysis, and data acquisition, including phenolic compounds, non-structural carbohydrates, and C/N estimation. J.N. contributed to investigation and formal analysis of phenolic metabolic profiles. P.Š. contributed to formal analysis, statistical analysis, and data synthesis. R.P. contributed to investigation, sample collection, and analysis of phenolic compounds. A.V. contributed to investigation, sample collection, and metabolite extraction. E.H. contributed to conceptualization and writing – review and editing, including critical revision of the manuscript. N.K. contributed to investigation, microscopy, and visualization. V.Š. contributed to funding acquisition, supervision, project administration, and writing – review and editing. All authors contributed to writing – review and editing and approved the final version of the manuscript.

DECLARATION OF GENERATIVE AI IN SCIENTIFIC WRITING

During the preparation of this work, the authors used ChatGPT (OpenAI) only to check the grammar and wording of the text. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

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Table 1: Generalized additive models (GAMs) relating each response variable (natural log-transformed where indicated) to ln(PPFD), temperature (°C), and their interaction. Models were fitted with mgcv using REML. The table reports the number of observations (n), adjusted R² (Adj. R²) and the effective degrees of freedom (EDF) and p-values for each smooth term. Reported p-values are from mgcv F-tests for s(ln(PPFD)), s(Temperature), and their interaction ti(ln(PPFD), temperature). Significance codes: *** p < 0.001, ** p < 0.01, * p < 0.05, ns p ≥ 0.05.

Response	n	Adj. R ²	PPFD		Temperature		Interaction	
			EDF	p_value	EDF	p_value	EDF	p_value
Fv/Fm	28	0.49	0	ns ≥ 0.05	0.95	*** < 0.001	1.91	* < 0.05
ln(D.W.)	84	0.83	2.73	*** < 0.001	2.95	*** < 0.001	2.28	*** < 0.001
C/N	84	0.88	0.99	*** < 0.001	2.79	*** < 0.001	0.92	ns ≥ 0.05
ln(NSC)	42	0.56	0.88	** < 0.01	1.13	ns 0.098	4.32	*** < 0.001
ln(PheCs)	42	0.49	1.28	*** < 0.001	2.36	*** < 0.001	0	ns ≥ 0.05
ln(UV-A shielding)	38	0.78	0.99	*** < 0.001	2.02	*** < 0.001	1.74	* < 0.05
ln(PheCs/D.W.)	42	0.72	1.26	* < 0.05	2.63	*** < 0.001	1.85	** < 0.01

Table 2: Comparison of generalized additive models fitted with bivariate smooths relating response variables to pairs of predictors. Models were fitted using mgcv with REML. The table reports the predictor combinations and corresponding response variables, sample size (n), adjusted R² (Adj. R²), effective degrees of freedom (EDF), and the significance of the bivariate smooth term (p_term). Significance codes: *** p < 0.001.

model	n	Adj. R ²	p_value	EDF
C/N × ln(NSC) → ln(PheCs)	42	0.247	*** < 0.001	4.22
C/N × ln(PheCs) → ln(DW)	42	0.445	*** < 0.001	11.04

Figure 1: Redundancy analysis (RDA) biplot showing the relationships between six selected response variables (black arrows) and two explanatory variables — temperature and log-transformed PPFD (white labels). Symbols represent sample scores for each combination of temperature and PPFD levels, with 68% confidence ellipses for groups with sufficient replication. RDA1 and RDA2 axes explain 35.9% and 17.6% of the variation in the response matrix, respectively. Longer arrows indicate stronger correlations with the ordination axes, and the direction of the arrows reflects the gradient of increasing variable values. Response variables were standardized to zero mean and unit variance prior to analysis.

Figure 2: Generalized additive model (GAM; a) results for Fv/Fm showing response surface of the interactive effects of natural log-transformed photosynthetic photon flux density (ln(PPFD), originally in $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) and temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$). Color gradients represent model-predicted values, with contour lines indicating equal predicted values. Symbols correspond to the sign of the mixed second derivative ($\partial^2 z / \partial x \partial y$) used to classify interaction types: circles indicate Synergy (positive interaction) and squares indicate Antagonism (negative interaction). (Right) Partial effects of (b) ln(PPFD) and (c) temperature on Fv/Fm, with the other predictor held constant at its median value. Black lines represent fitted smooth terms, shaded areas denote 95 % confidence intervals, and open circles indicate partial residuals. Rug plots along the x-axis show the distribution of observed values for each predictor. Effective degrees of freedom (edf) for each smooth are reported on the y-axis labels.

Figure 3: Generalized additive model (GAM) response surfaces showing the interactive effects of natural log-transformed photosynthetic photon flux density (ln(PPFD), originally in $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) and temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) on: (a) ln(D.W.) (b) C/N ratio, (c) ln(NSC), (d) ln(PheCs), (e) ln(UV-A shielding) and (f) ln(PheCs/D.W.) ratio. Panels (c) and (d) show concentrations expressed per unit dry weight (D.W.). Color gradients represent model-predicted values for each response variable. Contour lines indicate equal predicted values. Symbols correspond to the sign of the mixed second derivative ($\partial^2 z / \partial x \partial y$) used to classify interaction types: filled circles indicate Synergy (positive interaction), squares indicate Antagonism (negative interaction), and triangles represent points On boundary (near-zero interaction within adaptive tolerance).

Figure 4: Partial effects of $\ln(\text{PPFD})$ and temperature on six physiological or biochemical plant traits as estimated by generalized additive models (GAMs). Each panel shows the smooth term for one predictor while holding the other predictor constant at its median value. The y-axis represents the partial effect of the predictor on the response variable (centered smooth function) with effective degrees of freedom (edf) given in the label. Black solid lines indicate the fitted smooths and shaded grey areas represent the 95% confidence intervals. Open circles denote partial residuals and rug plots along the x-axes indicate the distribution of observed predictor values. Traits are $\ln(\text{D.W.})$, C/N ratio, $\ln(\text{NSC})$, $\ln(\text{PheCs})$, $\ln(\text{UV-A shielding})$ and $\ln(\text{PheCs}/\text{D.W.})$ ratio.

Figure 5: Accumulation of flavonoids in a cross section of an *Arabidopsis thaliana* leaf (wild type) under varying light and temperature conditions. Irradiance decreases from left to right, and temperature decreases from top to bottom. Positions R1–R7 and S1–S12 indicate the plant’s location within the gradient (R = row, S = column). The cross section is oriented with the adaxial side facing upward and the abaxial side facing downward.

Figure 56: Generalized additive model (GAM) response surfaces illustrating the joint effects of (a) natural log-transformed non-structural carbohydrates (ln(NSC)) and C/N ratio on natural log-transformed phenolic compounds (PheCs), and (b) natural log-transformed phenolic compounds (ln(PheCs)) and C/N ratio on dry weight (ln(D.W.)), estimated using bivariate smooths. Color gradients represent model-predicted values for each response variable, while contour lines indicate equal predicted values. Open circles denote observed data points. Response surfaces are shown only within the convex hull of the observed data.